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Space-Fractional FEM for Scale Sensitive Truss Structures - Theory and Implementation

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Abstract

The paper has two primary aims. The first considers elaboration of space-fractional (non-local) truss model (s-FTM) based on the principle of virtual work within the framework of space-Fractional Continuum Mechanics (s-FCM). The second encompasses the development of a space-fractional finite element method (s-FFEM) for s-FTM. It is important that s-FTM allows to model the scale-effect, even spatially variable. Moreover, classical (local) truss theory is obtained as a special case of s-FTM (from both, the theoretical and approximated points of view). The convergence of s-FFEM is discussed, whereas the presented computational examples show that arbitrary topological complexity of the truss is allowed.

Keywords: Space-Fractional FEM, space-fractional continuum mechanics, fractional calculus, non-local truss, micro-truss

1. Introduction

The development of micro-electro-mechanical systems (MEMS) and nano-electro-mechanical systems (NEMS) devices led to the necessity of elaborating specific models to predict their mechanical, thermomechanical, or other multifield problems behaviours, where scale-sensitivity is a dominant phenomenon [1]. Furthermore, starting from very simple structures of the above mentioned devices, like single bars [2, 3], beams [4, 5], plates [6], disks [7] or shells [8] it is more and more important to be able to model complex systems like trusses, frames, multi-plates or hybrid truss-beam-plate one. This is a consequence of recent progress in miniaturized systems like nanogenerators [9, 10], nanosensors [11, 12], biosensors [13, 14], nanoactuators [15, 16], nanoresonators [17, 18], fiber-reinforced materials [19], flexible electronics [20] or micro/- nanomotors [21] whose internal structural complexity is significant.

Among many models dedicated to such systems like strain-gradient theories [22, 23], microp-

olar theory [24, 25], surface elasticity theory [26, 27], couple stress theory [22], dipolar gradient elasticity theory [28] or peridynamic models [29], it appears that the one that bases on fractional analysis are preferable [30, 31]. It is because recent achievements in mechanical sciences have shown that the fractional calculus [32, 33] enables us to define extremely powerful models for physical phenomena predictions due to its important property that we have infinitely many definitions of fractional derivative operators; let us mention just a few i.e. Riemann (published posthumously) [34], Grunwald [35], Letnikov (1868) [36], Caputo [37], Λ -fractional derivative [38], Atangana–Baleanu [39], Hadamard [40], Tempered-Caputo [41], Gerasimov-Caputo [7], Katugampola [42] and many others. However, most of the above-mentioned papers deal with basic topological complexity, and that is why this paper aims to cover this gap, proposing a methodology allowing for arbitrary topological complexity within generalised truss theory, namely space-fractional trusses, defined using an energetic approach.

As stated above, the elaborated space-fractional truss model is based on the principle of virtual work within the framework of space-Fractional Continuum Mechanics (s-FCM) defined in [31]. The model inherits the scale-sensitivity of s-FCM, allows for arbitrary topological complexity, and moreover, introduces a new methodology of approximation, namely the space-fractional Finite Element Method (s-FFEM). It is important to emphasise that these attributes are major differences compared to previous papers dedicated to single structural elements and generalized finite difference technique imposed on a strong form [43, 44, 45, 46]. Furthermore, the s-FFEM, as a standard FEM technique for integer analysis, manifests the superiority compared to previous fractional differential equations approximations e.g. multi-step methods [47], quadratic interpolation [48], Sumudu transform method [49], finite difference method [5], Bernstein polynomials method [50] or collocation method [51] allowing for general domains as well as varied boundary conditions.

The following novelties can be defined:

- elaboration of space-fractional (non-local) truss model (s-FTM) based on the principle of virtual work, and analysis, for the first time, a static response of two-dimensional nano/micro-trusses within the framework of s-FCM,
- approximation of the space-fractional strains as a sum of local strains and higher-order terms,

- development of a m -node finite element adapted to s-FTM,
- evaluation of the convergence of the method relative to the number of nodes of the finite element,
- derivation of the non-local formulation for equilibrium at an arbitrary point or cut-out section.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the concept of space-fractional mechanics and the approximation of space-fractional strain. Section 3 presents the finite element formulation of the space-fractional truss. Section 4 is devoted to the two-dimensional arbitrarily shaped space-fractional truss structure. Section 5 provides illustrative examples of one- and two-dimensional trusses. Section 6 concludes the article.

2. Space-Fractional continuum

2.1. Space-fractional Continuum Mechanics

To include the scale effect, the theoretical basis for a truss member is defined in the framework of s-FCM, according to which the fractional Cauchy's small strains $\overset{\circ}{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ [31, 52] take the following form

$$\overset{\circ}{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \ell_f^{\alpha-1} \left(\overset{\alpha}{D}_{x_j} u_i(\mathbf{x}) + \overset{\alpha}{D}_{x_i} u_j(\mathbf{x}) \right), \quad (1)$$

where u_i are the components of the displacement vector, \mathbf{x} is a spatial variable, while the term $\overset{\alpha}{D}_x(\cdot)$ denotes Riesz-Caputo fractional derivative [53], namely,

$$\overset{\alpha}{D}_x u(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}{\Gamma(2)} \left({}_{x-\ell_f}^C D_x^\alpha u(x) - {}_x^C D_{x+\ell_f}^\alpha u(x) \right), \quad (2)$$

which is a combination of the left

$${}_{x-\ell_f}^C D_x^\alpha u(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_{x-\ell_f}^x (x-\tau)^{-\alpha} u'(\tau) d\tau, \quad (3)$$

and right

$${}_x^C D_{x+\ell_f}^\alpha u(x) = \frac{-1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_x^{x+\ell_f} (\tau-x)^{-\alpha} u'(\tau) d\tau \quad (4)$$

Caputo derivatives, where Γ is an Euler gamma function, $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ is the order of the fractional differential operator, and $\ell_f = \ell_f(x)$ is the length scales in direction x . Contrary to other non-local theories, it should be pointed out that the domain affecting the deformation does not occupy the entire body under consideration but is limited to the finite horizon from the considered material point x , and the size of this horizon correlates with the length scale ℓ_f (as illustrated schematically in Fig. 1). Both parameters α and ℓ_f are thought to be microstructure-related [54] and accountable for the mapping of scale effects. In addition, Eq. (1) reduces to the classical case for $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ and/or $\ell_f \rightarrow 0$ - cf. [55].

Figure 1: The left and right Caputo fractional derivatives as operators on the finite left-side and right-side domain of spatial interaction.

2.2. Approximation of space-fractional strains

The following considers the fractional derivative approximation as an infinite sum of higher-integer-order derivatives.

First, the left and right Caputo fractional derivatives (Eqs. (3÷4)) are transformed by adopting new variables,

$$t_1 = (x - \tau)^{1-\alpha} \quad \text{and} \quad t_2 = (\tau - x)^{1-\alpha}. \quad (5)$$

Then, their differentials are as follows,

$$\begin{cases} dt_1 = -(1 - \alpha)(x - \tau)^{-\alpha} d\tau & \rightarrow \frac{-1}{(1-\alpha)} dt_1 = (x - \tau)^{-\alpha} d\tau, \\ dt_2 = (1 - \alpha)(\tau - x)^{-\alpha} d\tau & \rightarrow \frac{1}{(1-\alpha)} dt_2 = (\tau - x)^{-\alpha} d\tau. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Then, substituting Eqs. (5-6) into Eqs. (3÷4) allows to get the following form for the left

$${}^C D_{x-\ell_f}^\alpha u(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1 - \alpha)} \int_{x-\ell_f}^x (x - \tau)^{-\alpha} u'(\tau) d\tau = \frac{1}{\Gamma(2 - \alpha)} \int_0^{\ell_f^{1-\alpha}} u'(x - t_1^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}) dt_1, \quad (7)$$

and right

$${}^C D_{x+\ell_f}^\alpha u(x) = \frac{-1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_x^{x+\ell_f} (\tau-x)^{-\alpha} u'(\tau) d\tau = \frac{-1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \int_0^{\ell_f^{1-\alpha}} u'(x+t_2^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}) dt_2, \quad (8)$$

Caputo derivatives, respectively.

Next, we use an approximation based on Taylor series [56, 57] to expand the functions $u'(x-t_1^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}})$ and $u'(x+t_2^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}})$ around a point x ,

$$u'(x-t_1^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}) = u'(x) - t_1^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}} u''(x) + t_1^{\frac{2}{1-\alpha}} \frac{1}{2!} u'''(x) - t_1^{\frac{3}{1-\alpha}} \frac{1}{3!} u^{iv}(x) + \dots = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k t_1^{\frac{k}{1-\alpha}}}{k!} u^{(k+1)}(x), \quad (9)$$

and

$$u'(x+t_2^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}) = u'(x) + t_2^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}} u''(x) + t_2^{\frac{2}{1-\alpha}} \frac{1}{2!} u'''(x) + t_2^{\frac{3}{1-\alpha}} \frac{1}{3!} u^{iv}(x) + \dots = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{t_2^{\frac{k}{1-\alpha}}}{k!} u^{(k+1)}(x). \quad (10)$$

Substituting Eqs. (9-10) into Eqs. (7-8), and then integrating leads to the expression of the Caputo fractional derivative as an infinite sum of higher-integer-order derivatives as follows, for the left

$${}^C D_{x-\ell_f}^\alpha u(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \int_0^{\ell_f^{1-\alpha}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k t_1^{\frac{k}{1-\alpha}}}{k!} u^{(k+1)}(x) dt = \frac{1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \ell_f^{1-\alpha} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k w_k \ell_f^k u^{(k+1)}(x) \right) \quad (11)$$

and right

$${}^C D_{x+\ell_f}^\alpha u(x) = \frac{-1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \int_0^{\ell_f^{1-\alpha}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{t_2^{\frac{k}{1-\alpha}}}{k!} u^{(k+1)}(x) dt = \frac{1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \ell_f^{1-\alpha} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} w_k \ell_f^k u^{(k+1)}(x) \right) \quad (12)$$

Caputo derivatives, respectively, where

$$w_k = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } k = 0 \\ \frac{1}{k!} \frac{1-\alpha}{k+1-\alpha} & \text{for } k \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

After all, substituting Eqs. (11÷12) into Eq. (2), gives Riesz Caputo fractional derivative as a infinite sum of higher-integer-order derivatives,

$${}_x^{\alpha} D u(x) = \ell_f^{1-\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k u^{(k+1)}(x). \quad (14)$$

Then, the non-local strain $\hat{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ Eq. (1) can be expressed as follow

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \left(\frac{\partial^{k+1}}{\partial x_j} u_i(x) + \frac{\partial^{k+1}}{\partial x_i} u_j(x) \right) \right], \quad (15)$$

which can also be split into classical Cauchy (local) strain ε_{ij} and higher-order (non-local) term,

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \underbrace{\varepsilon_{ij}}_{\text{local strain}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \left(\frac{\partial^{k+1}}{\partial x_j} u_i(x) + \frac{\partial^{k+1}}{\partial x_i} u_j(x) \right) \right]}_{\text{non-local term}}, \quad (16)$$

where

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} u_i + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} u_j \right). \quad (17)$$

3. Space-Fractional truss element

3.1. Element stiffness matrix

In the following, the finite element method (FEM) methodology is used to analyze the truss structures. We consider the space-fractional truss element in the local coordinate system (x', y') with m nodes - see Fig. 2. The axial displacement $u(x')$ is approximated as

$$u(x') = \mathbf{N} \mathbf{d}, \quad (18)$$

where \mathbf{N} means the shape functions vector,

$$\mathbf{N} = \{N_1(x'), N_2(x'), \dots, N_m(x')\}, \quad (19)$$

and \mathbf{d} is the nodal axial displacements vector

$$\mathbf{d} = \{d_{11}, d_{21}, \dots, d_{m1}\}^T. \quad (20)$$

Truss is an element subjected only to axial forces, therefore, the only non-zero strain occurs

Figure 2: The space-fractional truss element of length L^e with m nodes in the local (x', y') and global (x, y) coordinate systems.

along the bar axis, and according to Eq. (1), it is as follows,

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_{11} = \ell_f^{\alpha-1} \overset{\alpha}{D}_{x'} u(x'). \quad (21)$$

Meanwhile, the approximation of Eq. (21) (according to Eq. (15)) is

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_{11} = \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k u^{(k+1)}(x'), \quad (22)$$

or splitted to local ($\varepsilon_{11} = \frac{d}{dx'} u(x')$ - according to Eq. (16)) and non-local terms reads

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_{11} = \underbrace{\varepsilon_{11}(x')}_{\text{local term}} + \underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \varepsilon_{11}^{(k)}(x')}_{\text{non-local term}}. \quad (23)$$

Note that since the shape functions are polynomials of degree $(m - 1)$, the sum in Eqs. (22-23) can be cut off at $(m - 2)$, since the higher-order derivatives will be equal to 0 anyway.

It is clear that setting $\alpha = 1$ or $\ell_f = 0$, zeroes out the higher-order term in the the non-local strain (Eq. (23)), resulting in only local strain,

$$\hat{\varepsilon}_{11} = \varepsilon_{11} = \frac{d}{dx'} u(x'). \quad (24)$$

Next, the only non-zero stress $\hat{\sigma}_{11}$ is

$$\hat{\sigma}_{11} = \underbrace{E\varepsilon_{11}(x')}_{\text{local stress } \sigma_{11}} + \underbrace{E \sum_{k=1}^{m-2} w_k \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} \ell_f^k \varepsilon_{11}^{(k)}(x')}_{\text{non-local term}} = E \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k u^{(k+1)}(x'), \quad (25)$$

and in the consequence the normal force is

$$F^N = \int_A \hat{\sigma}_{11} dA = EA \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k u^{(k+1)}(x'), \quad (26)$$

where E is Young's modulus, and A is area of cross-section.

The stiffness matrix of the space-fractional truss element is derived using the principle of virtual work,

$$\delta U = \delta W, \quad (27)$$

where δU is the variation of the internal energy,

$$\delta U = \int_V \delta \hat{\varepsilon}_{11} \hat{\sigma}_{11} dV = EA \int_{L^e} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \delta u^{(k+1)}(x') \right) \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k u^{(k+1)}(x') \right) dL^e, \quad (28)$$

and δW is the variation of the external load,

$$\delta W = \int_{L^e} \delta u(x') p(x') dL^e, \quad (29)$$

where L^e is bar length, and $p(x)$ is the external load (cf. Fig.5). Then, substituting Eqs. (28-29)

to Eq. (27) leads to

$$EA \int_{L^e} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \delta u^{(k+1)}(x') \right) \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k u^{(k+1)}(x') \right) dL^e = \int_{L^e} \delta u(x') p(x') dL^e. \quad (30)$$

Next, we denote the k -order differentiation of the displacement $u(x')$ Eq. (18) as

$$u^{(k)}(x') = \frac{d^k}{dx'^k} \mathbf{N} \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{B}^k \mathbf{d}, \quad (31)$$

therefore Eq. (30) reads

$$EA \int_{L^e} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \mathbf{B}^{k+1} \delta \mathbf{d} \right)^T \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \mathbf{B}^{k+1} \mathbf{d} \right) dL^e = \int_{L^e} (\mathbf{N} \delta \mathbf{d})^T p_0 dL^e + \delta \mathbf{d}^T \mathbf{P}, \quad (32)$$

where p_0 is distributed force along the x' -axis and \mathbf{P} is vector of concentrated forces at the nodes. Finally, the equation of the space-fractional FEM is

$$\underbrace{\left[EA \int_{L^e} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \mathbf{B}^{k+1} \right)^T \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \mathbf{B}^{k+1} \right) dL^e \right]}_{\bar{\mathbf{K}}^e} \mathbf{d} = \underbrace{\int_{L^e} \mathbf{N}^T p_0 dL^e + \mathbf{P}}_{\bar{\mathbf{f}}^e}. \quad (33)$$

In consequence, a system of equations with unknown nodal displacements \mathbf{d} was obtained,

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}}^e \mathbf{d} = \bar{\mathbf{f}}^e, \quad (34)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{K}}^e$ is the stiffness matrix of the space-fractional truss element in the local coordinate system,

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}}^e = EA \int_{L^e} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \mathbf{B}^{k+1} \right)^T \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \mathbf{B}^{k+1} \right) dL^e, \quad (35)$$

and $\bar{\mathbf{f}}^e$ is the nodal force vector,

$$\bar{\mathbf{f}}^e = \int_{L^e} \mathbf{N}^T p_0 dL^e + \mathbf{P}. \quad (36)$$

To simplify the derivation of the stiffness matrix, the natural coordinates $\xi \in \langle -1, 1 \rangle$ are used.

The coordinate transformation is described as

$$x' = \frac{L^e}{2}(\xi + 1), \quad (37)$$

or alternatively as

$$\xi = \frac{2x'}{L^e} - 1. \quad (38)$$

In consequence, the local stiffness matrix (Eq. (35)) transformed to natural coordinates (ξ)

reads

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}}^e = EA \frac{L^e}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \mathbf{B}^{k+1} \left(\frac{2}{L^e} \right)^{k+1} \right)^T \left(\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \ell_f^k \mathbf{B}^{k+1} \left(\frac{2}{L^e} \right)^{k+1} \right) d\xi, \quad (39)$$

and similarly, the nodal force vector in natural coordinates (ξ) is

$$\bar{\mathbf{f}}^e = \frac{L^e}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \mathbf{N}^T p_0 d\xi + \delta \mathbf{d}^T \mathbf{P}. \quad (40)$$

After the transformation procedure to natural coordinates, it is possible to apply numerical integration using the Gauss-Legendre quadrature, where the analytical integration of a given function $g(\xi)$ over the domain space $\xi \in \langle -1, 1 \rangle$ is replaced by the weighted sum

$$\int_{-1}^1 g(\xi) d\xi = \sum_{i=1}^n g(\xi_i) w_i^G, \quad (41)$$

where w_i^G are the quadrature weights, ξ_i are the location of integration points and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is the number of integration points. Shape functions $N_i(\xi)$, as well as the variable length scale function $\ell_f(\xi)$, are assumed to be a polynomials, so the Gauss-Legendre quadrature will give accurate results if

$$\begin{cases} n \geq \frac{\max(2(m-2), 2(p(\ell_f) \cdot (m-3) + 1)) + 1}{2} & \text{for odd } m \text{ nodes,} \\ n \geq \frac{\max(2(m-2), 2(p(\ell_f) \cdot (m-2))) + 1}{2} & \text{for even } m \text{ nodes,} \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

where $p(\ell_f)$ means the degree of polynomial assumed for $\ell_f(\xi)$.

3.2. Length scale function

The length scale is interpreted as the surrounding that affects the material point considered. The concept of variable length scale $\ell_f = \ell_f(x) \equiv \ell_f(\xi)$, as a function that decreases at the boundaries, is borrowed from [58]. In following, the function is assumed to be smooth and continuous, with a range at each point that does not extend beyond the boundary of the bar ($x - \ell_f(x) \geq 0$ and $x + \ell_f(x) \leq L$). To demonstrate the impact of the adopted length scale

function, the following two versions of $\ell_f(\xi)$ are selected,

$$\begin{cases} \ell_f^I(\xi) = -\ell_f^{max}(\xi^4 - 1)^3, \\ \ell_f^{II}(\xi) = -\ell_f^{max}(\xi^2 - 1), \end{cases} \quad (43)$$

where ℓ_f^{max} means the maximum value of function $\ell_f(\xi)$. Fig. 3 shows the assumed $\ell_f(\xi)$ functions plotted for $\ell_f^{max} = \{1.0, 2.0\}$.

An important property of $\ell_f^I(\xi)$ is that the function not only assumes a value of zero at the edges, but also has first- and second-order derivatives equal to zero at these points, which impacts the resulting normal forces, as will be presented in following Section 5.

Figure 3: Length scale functions $\ell_f(\xi)$ according to Eq. (43) plotted for $\ell_f^{max} = \{1.0, 2.0\} \mu m$.

3.3. Shape functions

Due to the non-locality in the approach and the need to take into account that the response at a material point depends on information from its finite surroundings of size ℓ_f , it is necessary to use a higher-order shape function. Shape functions are constructed in a regular manner - so that each shape function has a value of 1 at its associated node and 0 at all other nodes. These functions are built on m Chebyshev nodes of the second kind [59, 60] to minimize the problem of the Runge phenomenon [61, 62], which is a problem oscillation at the edges of an interpolation interval that occurs when interpolating with polynomials of high degree for equally spaced interpolation points. Fig. 4 shows an example of shape functions $N_i(\xi)$ in natural coordinates $\xi \in \langle -1, 1 \rangle$ for a 4-node truss element, expressed by polynomials of order $(m - 1)$, i.e. of degree 3 in this example.

In addition, Appendix A contains the equations of the shape functions and the explicit form of stiffness matrix components (Eq. (39)) for $m = 4$ indicating additional terms due to the non-locality of the approach. Meanwhile, in Section 5, the influence of the m value on the solution convergence is studied.

Figure 4: Shape functions in natural coordinates $\xi \in \langle -1, 1 \rangle$ for $m = 4$ -node truss element.

3.4. Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions imply known displacement at certain nodes m_{bc} , and they are included by modifying the matrix $\bar{\mathbf{K}}^e$ and the vector $\bar{\mathbf{f}}^e$, which leads to a system of equations

$$\bar{K}_{ij}^e d_i = \bar{f}_i^e - \sum_{k \in m_{bc}} \bar{K}_{ik}^e d_k, \quad (44)$$

for $j \in (1 : m) \setminus \{m_{bc}\}$, and $i \in (1 : m) \setminus \{m_{bc}\}$. After including the boundary conditions, a system of equations reduced by the number of known displacements (boundary conditions) remains to be solved to determine the value of the remaining d_i - in the paper the LU factorization was applied to solve the system of linear equations.

3.5. Equilibrium at an arbitrary point /cut-out section

As a space-fractional truss element introduces generalized meaning of force equilibrium in a truss node, compared to traditional local truss formulation, let us consider its implication at

an arbitrary point/cut-out section.

Eq. (32) represents a weak form of the problem. Meanwhile, the equivalent strong form, obtained by integrating by parts of Eq. (32), is as follows

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \left(\overset{\circ}{\sigma}_{11} \ell_f^k \right)^{(k+1)} + \frac{p_0(x')}{A} = 0, \quad (45)$$

or in terms of normal force F^N it reads

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \left(F^N \ell_f^k \right)^{(k+1)} + p_0(x') = 0. \quad (46)$$

Eq. (46) enforces the equilibrium at each point along the bar's length. It is clear that the

Figure 5: An arbitrary cut section of the truss element.

truss as a whole structure as well as it's each individual section must meet the conditions of equilibrium. Fig. 5 shows a cut-out piece of the bar. To determine the equilibrium of this cut-out piece, Eq. (46) is integrated over its length $\Delta x'$,

$$\int_{x'_1}^{x'_2} \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \left(F^N \ell_f^k \right)^{(k+1)} dx' + \int_{x'_1}^{x'_2} p_0(x') dx' = 0, \quad (47)$$

and after integration it is (if we assume $p_0(x') = const$)

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \left(F^N \ell_f^k \right)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'_2} - \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k \left(F^N \ell_f^k \right)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'_1} + p_0 \Delta x' = 0. \quad (48)$$

It should be also noted that for $\alpha = 1$ and/or $\ell_f(\xi) = 0$ in Eq. (48), the standard force balance is valid

$$F^N(x'_2) - F^N(x'_1) + p_0 \Delta x' = 0. \quad (49)$$

Based on Eq. (48), it can also be deduced that the normal force at the support will be equal to the reaction force R only if $\ell_f = 0$, $\ell'_f = 0$ and $\ell''_f = 0$ at that point. Otherwise, there is the

and

$$L^e = \sqrt{(x_m - x_1)^2 + (y_m - y_1)^2}. \quad (55)$$

Then, stiffness matrix of truss element \mathbf{K}^e in global coordinate system is

$$\mathbf{K}^e = \mathbf{G}^T \bar{\mathbf{K}}^e \mathbf{G}, \quad (56)$$

and the element load vector is

$$\mathbf{F}^e = \mathbf{G}^T \bar{\mathbf{F}}^e. \quad (57)$$

Furthermore, a standard finite element assembly procedure is used to build the global stiffness matrix for the entire truss structure. The element stiffness matrices, defined in the global coordinate system, are merged into the global stiffness matrix by appropriate indexing and matrix-entry addition.

5. Numerical results

5.1. Results for 1D truss element

This section presents the non-local results for a micro-scaled single truss element. Two different bar configurations (Example 5.1 and Example 5.2) are used in numerical analyzes. In the examples, micro-bars of length $L^e = 10 \mu m$ and circular cross-section with a diameter of $d = 0.1 \mu m$ (area $A = \frac{\pi d^2}{4}$), made of steel with elastic modulus $E = 205 GPa$, are considered. The structure is discretised with a single truss element with m nodes.

Example 5.1. Consider that micro-bar is both-side fixed and subjected to a uniformly distributed load $p_0 = 10 \mu N/\mu m$ along its length (see Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Both-side fixed space-fractional truss of the length L^e loaded by a constant body force p_0 distributed in the truss axial direction x' .

Firstly, the effect of the number of element nodes m on the convergence of the solution is examined. Fig. 7 shows the maximum absolute displacement $\max|u(x')|$, maximum ab-

solute normal force $\max|F^N(x')|$, norm of the displacement $\|u(x')\|$ and norm of the normal force $\|F^N(x')\|$. The calculations were performed for varying number of nodes $m = \{3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 15, 21, 25, 31\}$, with the non-local parameters set to $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$ and $\ell_f^{max} = \{1.0 \mu m, 2.0 \mu m\}$.

The convergence depends on the adopted:

- α - the smaller its value, the greater the number of nodes m required;
- $\ell_f(\xi)$ function - the higher the polynomial degree, the greater the number of m nodes needed;
- the ℓ_f^{max} - the larger its value, the greater the number of nodes m required.

Based on the convergence of the solutions obtained, it was finally decided to use a 21-node finite truss element for the first length scale function ($\ell_f^I(\xi)$) and a 11-node element for the second one ($\ell_f^{II}(\xi)$) - Fig. 8 shows the corresponding displacement $u(x')$ and normal force $F^N(x')$.

Figure 7: a) Maximum absolute displacement $\max|u(x')|$; b) maximum absolute normal force $\max|F^N(x')|$; c) norm of the displacement $\|u(x')\|$; d) norm of the normal force $\|F^N(x')\|$; for $\ell_f^{max} = \{0.1L^e, 0.2L^e\}$, $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$, and $m = \{3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 15, 21, 25, 31\}$.

Noteworthy, the value of the normal force at the ends of the bars ($F^N(x' = 0)$ and $F^N(x' = L^e)$)

Figure 8: Example 5.1: displacement $u(x')$ and normal force $F^N(x')$; for $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$, and $m = 21$ (for ℓ_f^I) or $m = 11$ (for ℓ_f^{II}) (cf. Eq. (43)), and a) $\ell_f^{max} = 0.1L^e = 1.0 \mu m$ and b) $\ell_f^{max} = 0.2L^e = 2.0 \mu m$.

is equal to the support reaction value only for the first adopted length scale function ℓ_f^I , since at the ends, is not only the function equal to zero, but also its first- and second-order derivatives - cf. Eq. (48). However, the equilibrium is satisfied for both ℓ_f^I as well as ℓ_f^{II} . Fig. 9 illustrates the left side of the bar cut at an arbitrary point x'_2 , while the corresponding equilibrium equation is

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k (F^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'_2} + p_0 \Delta x' - R_1 = 0, \quad (58)$$

where $R_1 = 50 \mu N$ is support reaction. Additionally, Table 1 collects relative percentage difference of the equilibrium Eq. (58),

$$\text{error} = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k (F^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'_2} + p_0 \Delta x' - R_1}{R_1} \times 100\% \quad (59)$$

at the coordinate $x'_2 = \{0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0\} \mu m$, for two length scale functions ℓ_f^I and ℓ_f^{II} , for $\ell_f^{max} = 1.0 \mu m$, and $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$.

Figure 9: The left side of the bar cut of the truss examined in Example 5.1 (cf. Fig. 6) at an arbitrary point x'_2 .

Table 1: Example 5.1: percentage error of the equilibrium Eq. (59) at coordinate $x'_2 = \{0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0\} \mu m$, for two length scale functions ℓ_f^I (with $m = 21$ node element) and ℓ_f^{II} (with $m = 11$ node element), for $\ell_f^{max} = 0.1L^e = 1.0 \mu m$, and $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$.

x'_2 [μm]	error [%]						
	$\alpha = 1.0$	ℓ_f^I			ℓ_f^{II}		
		$\alpha = 0.8$	$\alpha = 0.6$	$\alpha = 0.4$	$\alpha = 0.8$	$\alpha = 0.6$	$\alpha = 0.4$
0.0	6.76×10^{-8}	-3.06×10^{-2}	-1.24×10^{-1}	-1.42×10^{-1}	-2.17×10^{-4}	-4.70×10^{-4}	-6.64×10^{-4}
1.0	-5.56×10^{-8}	2.38×10^{-2}	1.43×10^{-2}	-1.55×10^{-3}	-5.48×10^{-5}	-1.22×10^{-4}	-1.79×10^{-4}
2.0	-2.66×10^{-8}	9.46×10^{-3}	2.44×10^{-3}	-4.07×10^{-3}	4.21×10^{-5}	9.50×10^{-5}	1.41×10^{-4}
3.0	1.77×10^{-8}	5.40×10^{-3}	-5.64×10^{-4}	-4.16×10^{-3}	-4.41×10^{-5}	-9.93×10^{-5}	-1.47×10^{-4}
4.0	2.52×10^{-8}	-6.29×10^{-3}	-1.21×10^{-3}	2.01×10^{-3}	3.17×10^{-5}	7.12×10^{-5}	1.05×10^{-4}
5.0	2.84×10^{-14}	-4.69×10^{-9}	-1.32×10^{-9}	-4.46×10^{-10}	-4.55×10^{-13}	1.29×10^{-12}	-2.12×10^{-12}

Example 5.2. Consider that micro-bar is left-side fixed and subjected to a point load $P = 10 \mu N$ applied at its right end (see Fig. 10).

Figure 10: Left-side fixed bar of the length L^e loaded by a constant body force p_0 distributed in the truss axial direction x' .

Figure 11: Example 5.2: a) displacement $u(x')$ and b) normal force $F^N(x')$; for $\ell_f^{max} = 0.1L^e$, $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$, and $m = 21$ for ℓ_f^I or $m = 11$ for ℓ_f^{II} (cf. Eq. (43)).

Fig. 11 shows the displacement $u(x')$ and normal force $F^N(x')$ for different values of $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$, two length scale functions ℓ_f^I , ℓ_f^{II} and $\ell_f^{max} = 1.0 \mu m$. There are no significant differences in displacements, however, notable differences are observed in the normal forces. Worth noting is that the volume average of the strain

$$\langle \varepsilon_{11} \rangle = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \varepsilon_{11}(x) dV, \quad (60)$$

and in the consequence the volume average of stress

$$\langle \sigma_{11} \rangle = E \langle \varepsilon_{11} \rangle = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \hat{\sigma}_{11}(x) dV, \quad (61)$$

and the average of normal force

$$\langle F^N \rangle = EA \langle \varepsilon_{11} \rangle = \frac{1}{L^e} \int_{L^e} F^N(x) dL^e \quad (62)$$

equal always the value of macro- strain / stress / normal force, regardless of α and $\ell_f(\xi)$. That is, in Example 5.2, $\langle F^N \rangle = 10 \mu N$ in each case considered.

Additionally, Fig. 12 illustrates the left side of the bar cut at an arbitrary point x'_2 , while the corresponding equilibrium equation is

$$\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k (F^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'_2} - R_1 = 0, \quad (63)$$

where $R_1 = 10 \mu N$ is support reaction. Meanwhile, Table 2 collects relative percentage difference of the equilibrium Eq. (63),

$$\text{error} = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1 + (-1)^k}{2} w_k (F^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'_2} - R_1}{R_1} \times 100\% \quad (64)$$

at the coordinate $x'_2 = \{0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0\} \mu m$, for two length scale functions ℓ_f^I and ℓ_f^{II} , for $\ell_f^{max} = 1.0 \mu m$, and $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$.

Figure 12: The left side of the bar cut of the truss examined in Example 5.2 (cf. Fig. 10) at an arbitrary point x'_2 .

5.2. Results for 2D truss structure

This section presents the non-local results for a nano/micro-scaled truss structure defined in a two-dimensional plane. The adopted truss configuration is analyzed in Example 5.3.

Table 2: Example 5.2: percentage error of the equilibrium Eq. (64) at coordinate $x'_2 = \{0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0\} \mu m$, for two length scale functions ℓ_f^I (with $m = 21$ node element) and ℓ_f^{II} (with $m = 11$ node element), for $\ell_f^{max} = 0.1L^e = 1.0 \mu m$, and $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$.

x'_2 [μm]	error [%]						
	ℓ_f^I				ℓ_f^{II}		
	$\alpha = 1.0$	$\alpha = 0.8$	$\alpha = 0.6$	$\alpha = 0.4$	$\alpha = 0.8$	$\alpha = 0.6$	$\alpha = 0.4$
0.0	3.97×10^{-8}	9.48×10^{-3}	-1.13×10^{-1}	-2.22×10^{-1}	-1.90×10^{-4}	-4.55×10^{-4}	-6.72×10^{-4}
1.0	8.60×10^{-8}	3.73×10^{-2}	1.44×10^{-2}	-2.40×10^{-2}	-5.33×10^{-5}	-1.29×10^{-4}	-1.92×10^{-4}
2.0	3.67×10^{-8}	2.69×10^{-2}	2.30×10^{-2}	1.52×10^{-2}	4.16×10^{-5}	1.00×10^{-4}	1.51×10^{-4}
3.0	-7.22×10^{-8}	-5.81×10^{-3}	-6.20×10^{-3}	-6.94×10^{-3}	-1.79×10^{-5}	-4.29×10^{-5}	-6.38×10^{-5}
4.0	5.65×10^{-9}	-8.62×10^{-3}	-3.66×10^{-3}	2.76×10^{-3}	-1.87×10^{-5}	-4.56×10^{-5}	-6.98×10^{-5}
5.0	8.48×10^{-8}	1.25×10^{-2}	5.89×10^{-3}	-2.69×10^{-3}	3.78×10^{-5}	9.17×10^{-5}	1.39×10^{-4}

Example 5.3. Consider the truss structure of the scheme depicted in Fig. 13. Each bar is of length $L^e = 2 \mu m$, elastic modulus $E = 205 \text{ GPa}$ and circular cross-section with diameter $d = 0.1 \mu m$ (area $A = \frac{\pi d^2}{4}$). The truss is subjected to a point force $P_m = 10 \mu N$ applied at node 1. Each bar is discretized with a single finite element with m nodes.

Figure 13: Example 5.3: Adopted two-dimensional truss configuration with 3 connecting nodes between truss members.

Since Example 5.2 demonstrated that there are no significant differences in displacements between the local and non-local solutions, Figs. 14-15 present only the obtained normal forces for $\ell_f(\xi) = \{\ell_f^I, \ell_f^{II}\}$, $\ell_f^{max} = \{0.2 \mu m, 0.3 \mu m\}$ and $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$.

Figure 14: Example 5.3: normal force $F^N(x')$; for local truss element ($\alpha = 1.0$); and non-local space-fractional truss element for $\ell_f^{max} = 0.1L^e = 0.2 \mu m$, $\alpha = \{0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$, and $m = 21$ for ℓ_f^I (orange lines) or $m = 11$ for ℓ_f^{II} (green lines).

Additionally, Fig. 16 illustrates the truss members sectioned near the supports, while Eqs. (65-66) provide the corresponding equilibrium equations in horizontal and vertical directions, respectively, at node 1,

$$\begin{cases} \sum F_x = \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1+(-1)^k}{2} w_k (F_1^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'=L^e} \cos(60^\circ) - \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1+(-1)^k}{2} w_k (F_2^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'=L^e} \cos(60^\circ) = 0, \\ \sum F_y = P + \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1+(-1)^k}{2} w_k (F_1^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'=L^e} \sin(60^\circ) + \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1+(-1)^k}{2} w_k (F_2^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'=L^e} \sin(60^\circ) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (65)$$

and at node 2,

$$\begin{cases} \sum F_x = R_{H2} + \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1+(-1)^k}{2} w_k (F_3^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'=0} + \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1+(-1)^k}{2} w_k (F_1^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'=0} \cos(60^\circ) = 0, \\ \sum F_y = R_{V2} + \sum_{k=0}^{m-2} \frac{1+(-1)^k}{2} w_k (F_1^N \ell_f^k)^{(k)} \Big|_{x'=0} \sin(60^\circ) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (66)$$

Figure 15: Example 5.3: normal force $F^N(x')$; for local truss element ($\alpha = 1.0$); and non-local space-fractional truss element for $\ell_f^{max} = 0.15L^e = 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, $\alpha = \{0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$, and $m = 21$ for ℓ_f^I (orange lines) or $m = 11$ for ℓ_f^{II} (green lines).

where $R_{H2} = 0$ and $R_{V2} = R_{V3} = 5 \mu\text{N}$ are the support reactions. The truss is symmetrical, therefore, the equilibrium equations at node 3 are analogous to those at node 2. Table 3 collects the results of the left-side of Eqs. (65)-(66) calculated for two length scale functions ℓ_f^I and ℓ_f^{II} , $\ell_f^{max} = 0.15L^e = 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, and $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$.

The average of normal force $\langle F^N \rangle$ Eq. (62) in all considered cases is equal to the value of macro-normal force, i.e. $\langle F^N \rangle = -5.77 \mu\text{N}$ for bars of nodes 1-2 and 1-3, and $\langle F^N \rangle = 2.89 \mu\text{N}$ for bar of nodes 2-3.

Figure 16: Truss elements cut near the supports.

Table 3: Left-side of Eqs. (65)-(66) calculated for two length scale functions ℓ_f^I (with $m = 21$ node element) and ℓ_f^{II} (with $m = 11$ node element), for $\ell_f^{max} = 0.15L^e = 0.3 \mu m$, and $\alpha = \{1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.4\}$.

		Error [μm]			
α	direction	ℓ_f^I		ℓ_f^{II}	
		node 1	node 2 / node 3	node 1	node 2 / node 3
1.0	$\sum F_x$	0.0	2.53×10^{-12}	0.0	2.53×10^{-12}
	$\sum F_y$	-3.98×10^{-9}	-1.99×10^{-9}	-3.98×10^{-9}	-1.99×10^{-9}
0.8	$\sum F_x$	0.0	1.15×10^{-9}	0.0	1.13×10^{-12}
	$\sum F_y$	-7.99×10^{-2}	-3.99×10^{-2}	1.18×10^{-3}	5.92×10^{-4}
0.6	$\sum F_x$	0.0	-1.28×10^{-8}	0.0	1.81×10^{-12}
	$\sum F_y$	-5.10×10^{-2}	-2.55×10^{-2}	3.01×10^{-3}	1.51×10^{-3}
0.4	$\sum F_x$	0.0	-1.21×10^{-8}	0.0	3.60×10^{-12}
	$\sum F_y$	1.08×10^{-1}	5.40×10^{-2}	4.54×10^{-3}	2.27×10^{-3}

6. Conclusions

This paper elaborates on the space-fractional (non-local) truss model (s-FTM) based on the principle of virtual work, and introduces, for the first time, a static analysis of two-dimensional nano/micro-trusses within the framework of space-fractional continuum mechanics. A m -node finite element model tailored for the non-local (space-fractional) truss has been developed. The approach employs the approximation of fractional derivatives using a sum of higher-order integer derivatives, demonstrating also that fractional strains can be expressed as the sum of local strains and a higher-order term. The convergence of the proposed method in relation to the number of element nodes was evaluated. Furthermore, a non-local formulation for equilibrium

at an arbitrary point or cut-out section has been derived.

The main findings are as follows:

- required number of element nodes m depends on the adopted distribution of length scale function ℓ_f , as well as the values of ℓ_f^{max} and α ,
- the resulting displacements and normal forces depend on the distribution of ℓ_f , as well as the values of ℓ_f^{max} and α ,
- the effect of non-locality is more pronounced in the distribution of normal force than the displacement,
- the average strain, stress, or normal force corresponds to the macro strain, stress, or normal force.

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Appendix A

The appendix contains formulas for shape functions and stiffness matrix components for a 4-node element ($m = 4$). For 7-, 11- and 21-node elements ($m = \{7, 11, 21\}$), the formulas can be found in the research data available here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234890>.

Formulas for shape functions $N_i(\xi)$ for $m = 4$ are as follows,

$$\begin{cases} N_1 = \frac{-2\xi^3}{3} + \frac{2\xi^2}{3} + \frac{\xi}{6} - \frac{1}{6}; \\ N_2 = \frac{4\xi^3}{3} - \frac{2\xi^2}{3} - \frac{4\xi}{3} + \frac{2}{3}; \\ N_3 = \frac{-4\xi^3}{3} - \frac{2\xi^2}{3} + \frac{4\xi}{3} + \frac{2}{3}; \\ N_4 = \frac{2\xi^3}{3} + \frac{2\xi^2}{3} - \frac{\xi}{6} - \frac{1}{6}. \end{cases} \quad (67)$$

Formulas for stiffness matrix components \bar{K}_{ij}^e of the element in local natural coordinate system ($\xi \in \langle -1, 1 \rangle$) for $m = 4$ (additional terms related to non-locality are marked in blue - their omission, by assuming $\alpha = 1$ or $\ell_f(x) = 0$, results in a local solution), are as follows,

$$\begin{cases} \bar{K}_{11}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(-2\xi^2 + \frac{4}{3}\xi + \frac{1}{6})}{L} - \frac{16\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right]^2 d\xi; \\ \bar{K}_{12}^e = \bar{K}_{21}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(-2\xi^2 + \frac{4}{3}\xi + \frac{1}{6})}{L} - \frac{16\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] \left[\frac{2(4\xi^2 - \frac{4}{3}\xi - \frac{4}{3})}{L} + \frac{32\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] d\xi; \\ \bar{K}_{13}^e = \bar{K}_{31}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(-2\xi^2 + \frac{4}{3}\xi + \frac{1}{6})}{L} - \frac{16\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] \left[\frac{2(-4\xi^2 - \frac{4}{3}\xi + \frac{4}{3})}{L} - \frac{32\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] d\xi; \\ \bar{K}_{14}^e = \bar{K}_{41}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(-2\xi^2 + \frac{4}{3}\xi + \frac{1}{6})}{L} - \frac{16\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] \left[\frac{2(2\xi^2 + \frac{4}{3}\xi - \frac{1}{6})}{L} + \frac{16\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] d\xi; \\ \bar{K}_{22}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(4\xi^2 - \frac{4}{3}\xi - \frac{4}{3})}{L} + \frac{32\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right]^2 d\xi; \\ \bar{K}_{23}^e = \bar{K}_{32}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(4\xi^2 - \frac{4}{3}\xi - \frac{4}{3})}{L} + \frac{32\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] \left[\frac{2(-4\xi^2 - \frac{4}{3}\xi + \frac{4}{3})}{L} - \frac{32\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] d\xi; \\ \bar{K}_{24}^e = \bar{K}_{42}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(4\xi^2 - \frac{4}{3}\xi - \frac{4}{3})}{L} + \frac{32\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] \left[\frac{2(2\xi^2 + \frac{4}{3}\xi - \frac{1}{6})}{L} + \frac{16\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] d\xi; \\ \bar{K}_{33}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(-4\xi^2 - \frac{4}{3}\xi + \frac{4}{3})}{L} - \frac{32\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right]^2 d\xi; \\ \bar{K}_{34}^e = \bar{K}_{43}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(-4\xi^2 - \frac{4}{3}\xi + \frac{4}{3})}{L} - \frac{32\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] \left[\frac{2(2\xi^2 + \frac{4}{3}\xi - \frac{1}{6})}{L} + \frac{16\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right] d\xi; \\ \bar{K}_{44}^e = EA \frac{L}{2} \int_{-1}^1 \left[\frac{2(2\xi^2 + \frac{4}{3}\xi - \frac{1}{6})}{L} + \frac{16\ell_f^2(1-\alpha)}{L^3(3-\alpha)} \right]^2 d\xi. \end{cases} \quad (68)$$